

Effect of 1,10-phenanthroline on the graft polymerization of vinyl monomers onto guar gum in presence of Fenton's reagent

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Abstract : The effect and role of 1,10-phenanthroline and *ortho* phosphoric acid on graft polymerization of vinyl monomers onto guar gum in presence of Fenton's reagent have been studied. Reaction conditions were optimized. FTIR spectra were used for confirmation of grafting. A probable mechanism of grafting to elucidate the role of phenanthroline and phosphoric has been suggested. Thermal properties of the grafted polymer were studied.

Keywords : Guar gum, grafting, Fenton's reagent, electrode potential.

Guar gum (GG) is derived from the seeds of guar gum plant (*Cyamopsis tetragonolobus*), a pod-bearing legume grown commercially in India, Pakistan and United States¹. Guar gum has chains of 1-4 linked β -D-mannopyranosyl and 1-6 linked α -D-galactopyranosyl¹. It is being used as a viscosity builder and water binder in many industries such as textile, food, paper, petroleum, pharmaceuticals, etc.^{2,3}.

Large volumes of research workers are actively engaged in chemical grafting of GG to modify its properties. The GG itself suffers from the following drawbacks^{4,5}: (i) low shear stability, (ii) inferior thermal stability, (iii) low effective drug reducer, (iv) susceptible to easy biodegradation, (v) low metal ion uptake capacity, (vi) low flocculation rate and (vii) low flock strength. Singh and their co-workers⁴ studied grafting of acrylamide onto GG to improve its drug reduction behavior. Behari *et al.*⁶ grafted acrylic acid with GG to improve its metal ion uptake capacity. Taunk and his colleagues⁷, reported grafting of methacrylamide onto GG to obtain efficient flocculating agents for industrial effluents containing metallic and non-metallic contaminants. Recently Behari *et al.*⁸ synthesized graft copolymer of guar gum with *N*-vinyl formamide. Several metals ions have been used^{9,10} as an initiator for grafting reaction. Ceric ion was found to be most efficient and selective initiator for grafting GG¹. Very few works are published on the used of Fenton's reagent ($\text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$) as an initiator for vinyl graft polymerization¹¹⁻¹⁷. Ferric/ferrous inter conversation is a single step one electron transfer process and produces hydroxyl free radicals (HO^\bullet) in presence of hydrogen

peroxide and vinyl monomers. The produced free radicals thus preferably lead to vinyl polymerization, rather than vinyl graft polymerization. However, the presence of phenanthroline and phosphoric acid change the activity of Fenton's reagent towards vinyl grafting¹⁵.

The present investigation involves the studies on the effect and role of phosphoric acid and phenanthroline towards graft polymerization of vinyl monomers onto guar gum, initiated by Fenton's reagent.

Experimental

Materials : Guar gum (GG) was procured from S. K. Chemical (Kolkata, India) and subjected to Soxhlet extraction. Methyl methacrylate (MMA), ethyl methacrylate (EMA) and methyl acrylate were purchased from Merck, Schuchardt, Germany. Hydrogen peroxide (Qualigens, India), ferrous ammonium sulfate (FAS) (Merck, India), 1,10-phenanthroline (B.D.H., UK) and phosphoric acid (Aldrich) were used as received. All other chemicals and solvents were analytical grade and used without further purification.

Graft polymerization : Graft polymerization was carried out in a two necked round bottomed flask that was kept in a constant temperature bath maintained at the required temperature. A definite amount of GG was soaked with a requisite quantity of vinyl monomers for 15 min before graft polymerization started. Water, H_2SO_4 , H_2O_2 , ferrous ammonium sulfate (FAS) and complex forming agents (H_3PO_4 , phenanthroline) were then added. Nitrogen atmosphere was then maintained throughout the entire

reaction period. After the specific time interval, the reaction was arrested by quenching with hydroquinone. To remove homopolymer, the sample was precipitated with acetone. Finally the sample was extracted with acetone in a Soxhlet apparatus for 4 h to dissolve all the homopolymers. The colorless product was dried under vacuum at 50 °C for >24 h to a constant weight.

Determination of graft level : The percentage of grafting (PG), grafting efficiency (GE), percentage of homopolymer (H) formation and average rate of grafting (R_g) were determined by the following formulas respectively¹⁸⁻²².

$$PG (\%) = 100(W_2 - W_1)/W_1 \quad (1)$$

$$GE (\%) = 100(W_2 - W_1)/W_3 \quad (2)$$

$$H (\%) = 100(W_4 - W_1)/W_4 \quad (3)$$

$$R_g (\text{mol s}^{-1} \text{m}^3) = (W_2 - W_1)/M.t.v \quad (4)$$

where W_1 is the weight of the original GG taken, W_2 is the weight of the grafted product after Soxhlet extraction (homo-polymer free), W_3 is the weight of the monomer charged and W_4 is that of the product before extraction (grafted product + homo-polymer). M is the molecular weight of the monomer, t is the reaction time in second and v is the volume in m^3 of the reaction mixture.

Characterization : Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of the sample were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR-8400S model in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} . Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was conducted using a Stanton Redcraft Thermal Analyzer (STA 780) in air at a rate of 10 °C/min. The pH of the solution was measured by a

pH meter (Elico, India LI-120). Flow time of the grafted polymer in dimethyl sulfoxide solution was measured by an Ubbelohde Viscometer.

Results and discussion

Evidence of grafting by FTIR spectroscopy : The presence of vinyl polymer (e.g. polymethyl methacrylate) on the GG molecule was verified by the FTIR spectra of GG and GG-g-PMMA (grafted guar gum). The FTIR spectra of the polymers are shown in Fig. 1. Both the spectra of GG and grafted polymer show a characteristic broad absorption band of hydroxyl group around 3500–3000 cm^{-1} . This is attributed to the O–H bond stretching vibration of GG^{14,23}. The spectrum of the methyl methacrylate treated GG exhibits a strong absorption band at 1730 cm^{-1} , which is absent in the spectrum of GG. The peak at 1730 cm^{-1} could be associated with the C=O stretching vibration of an ester group^{15,24} from MMA. The appearance of a new peak at 1730 cm^{-1} in the resulted copolymer provides strong evidence of grafting. Similarly, the grafting by other vinyl monomers (EMA, MA) may be established by FTIR spectra.

Thermal properties of the grafted polymer : Thermal properties of the grafted polymer (51% grafting) and original polymer (GG) were studied with the help of $dw(\%)/dT$ (percentage of weight loss with respect to temperature) vs temperature plot (Fig. 2). The slopes of the lines are interestingly different for GG and GG-g-PMMA for temperature range of 30 to 450 °C. The slope for the grafted material is less than that of natural polymer

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of (A) GG and (B) GG-g-PMMA.

Fig. 2. The $dw(\%)/dT$ vs temperature plot of GG and GG-g-PMMA.

(GG). The slopes indicate clearly the better thermal stability of the grafted polymer with respect to pure GG within the specified temperature range.

Effect of phenanthroline and phosphoric acid : The Table 1 shows the effect of phenanthroline towards grafting of MMA onto GG in presence of Fenton's reagent. The

Table 1. Experimental results

System	Phenanthroline (g/dL)	Phosphoric acid (mL/dL)	PG (%)	GE (%)	R_g (mol s ⁻¹ m ⁻³)
S ₁	0	0	41.50	43.62	3.3×10^{-3}
S ₂	0.1	0	51.00	54.26	4.0×10^{-3}
S ₃	0	5	35.60	37.87	2.8×10^{-3}

Recipe : GG = 1 g/dL, MMA = 0.94 g/dL, H₂SO₄ = 0.036 mol/dL, FAS = 3.2×10^{-4} mol/dL, H₂O₂ = 1.76×10^{-2} mol/dL, temp. = 50 °C, time = 3.5 h.

presence of phenanthroline increases the PG, GE and R_g to a considerable extent. On the other hand, introduction of H₃PO₄ decreases the grafting level.

Such type of observation may be explained on the basis of effect of complex formation on the standard reduction potential. Phenanthroline forms more stable complex with ferrous ion than ferric ion¹⁶. As a result, the reduction potential of the Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺ system increases from 0.76 volt to 1.12 volt at 25 °C, and this increase is significant at the temperature of polymerization. The increase in reduction potential is probably responsible for higher grafting efficiency of the Fenton's reagent. The oxidizing power of Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺ increases with the increase of reduction potential. As a result the production of guar gum macro radical (GG[•]) is enhanced through

one electron transfer process (eq. (7)). Phosphoric acid, on the other hand forms a stable complex with Fe³⁺ than Fe²⁺. Such complex formation reduces the oxidizing power of Fe³⁺. The reduction potential of the Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺ system reduces to 0.67 volt at 25 °C. Thus it may be concluded that the presence of phenanthroline activates the Fenton's reagent while H₃PO₄ deactivates the efficiency towards grafting.

Search for optimum [H₂O₂]/[Fe²⁺] mole ratio (H/I) : The results obtained by changing the [H₂O₂]/[Fe²⁺] mole ratio (H/I) (from 1.38 to 69.20) on the PG, GE, H and R_g are shown in Table 2. At the H/I mole ratio of 0.5, no polymer was formed. There was color change of the

Table 2. Effect of H₂O₂/Fe²⁺ (H/I) mole ratio

H/I mole ratio	PG (%)	GE (%)	H (%)	R_g (mol s ⁻¹ m ⁻³)
1.38	0	0	5.60	0
27.68	10	10.64	15.12	7.9×10^{-4}
41.52	47	50.00	12.21	3.7×10^{-3}
55.00	51	54.26	10.70	4.0×10^{-3}
69.20	45	47.87	16.10	3.6×10^{-3}

Recipe : GG = 1 g/dL, MMA = 0.94 g/dL, H₂SO₄ = 0.036 mol/dL, FAS = 3.2×10^{-4} mol/dL, phenanthroline = 0.1 g/dL, temp. = 50 °C, time = 3.5 h.

solution from red to blue, indicating the formation of ferric phenanthroline complex¹⁶ (eq. (5)).

At the H/I mole ratio of 1, only 5.6% homopolymer was formed. The formation of homopolymer may be explained with the help of (eq. (6)), as stated below.

The produced HO[•] free radicals then lead to formation of homopolymers through free radical mechanism. At the mole ratio beyond 1.38, both homopolymer and grafted polymer are produced. The formation of the grafted polymers may be explained by the following chemical equation (eq. (7)).

The intermediately produced GG[•] macro radical initiates graft polymerization. A small amount of acid is required

to resist the hydrolysis of iron salt. However, excess acid diminishes the formation of graft polymer by withdrawing HO^- from the system. The extent of grafting is increased sharply with the increase of mole ratio up to 55. This increase of grafting level may be attributed to the formation of larger amount of GG macro radical with the addition of more H_2O_2 . The optimum H/I mole ratio was found to be 55, which indicates that the catalytic amount of Fe^{2+} is required for grafting purpose. Eqs. (6) and (7) clearly explain the catalytic activity of Fe^{2+} . Eqs. (6) and (7), ultimately lead to eq. (8).

The percentage of homo-polymerization (H%) becomes low (10.7%) at the optimum mole ratio. However, the rate of grafting, R_g becomes comparatively high (4.0×10^{-3}) at same mole ratio.

Graft mechanism : The rate of graft polymerization is largely dependent on the concentration of monomer and initiator at a particular level of acid and GG. The relationship between (a) R_g and $[\text{MMA}]$ and (b) R_g and $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]^{1/2}$ (Figs. 3 and 4 respectively) are linear, indicating graft polymerization is first order with respect to monomer and half order to initiator concentration. Therefore, the following rate equation is established.

$$R_g = k. [\text{MMA}]. [\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]^{1/2} \quad (9)$$

where k is the rate constant for the graft polymerization at 50°C .

Fig. 3. Variation of R_g with $[\text{MMA}]$ at particular level of other reagents (GG = 1 g/dL, H_2SO_4 = 0.036 mol/dL, H/I mol ratio = 55, time = 3.5 h, temp. = 50°C).

Fig. 4. Variation of R_g with $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]^{1/2}$ at particular level of other reagents (GG = 1 g/dL, H_2SO_4 = 0.036 mol/dL, MMA = 0.94 g/dL, FAS = 3.2×10^{-4} mol/dL, time = 3.5 h, temp. = 50°C).

The mechanism of grafting is suggested as follows :

GGH and M represents guar gum and monomer respectively. The following rate expansions are derived on the basis of the reaction shown in eqs. (10)–(13) and steady state assumption for the free radicals GG^\bullet and GGM_n^\bullet

$$d[\text{GG}^\bullet]/dt = k_i [\text{GGH}] [\text{H}_2\text{O}_2] - k_{ii} [\text{GG}^\bullet] [\text{M}] = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$[\text{GG}^\bullet] = k_i [\text{H}_2\text{O}_2] [\text{GGH}] / k_{ii} [\text{M}] \quad (15)$$

$$d[\text{GGM}_n^\bullet]/dt = k_{ii} [\text{GG}^\bullet] [\text{M}] - k_t [\text{GGM}_n^\bullet]^2 = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$[\text{GGM}_n^\bullet] = (k_i/k_t)^{1/2} \cdot [\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]^{1/2} \cdot [\text{GGH}]^{1/2} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} R_g &= k_p [\text{GGM}_n^\bullet] [\text{M}] \\ &= k_p \cdot (k_i/k_t)^{1/2} \cdot [\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]^{1/2} \cdot [\text{M}] \cdot [\text{GGH}]^{1/2} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

At a particular level of GGH, eq. (18) becomes

$$R_g = \text{Constant} [\text{M}] \cdot [\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]^{1/2} \quad (19)$$

Eq. (19) is identical with eq. (9), established from experiment.

The PG of MMA onto GG at different reaction periods

Table 3. Variation of reaction time

Time (h)	PG (%)	pH
1	11.3	4.4
2	22.5	4.3
3	45.1	4.4
3.5	51.0	4.4
4	52.2	4.4

Recipe : GG = 1 g/dL, MMA = 0.94 g/dL, H₂SO₄ = 0.036 mol/dL, FAS = 3.2 × 10⁻⁴ mol, H₂O₂ = 0.0176 mol/dL, phenanthroline = 0.1 g, temp. = 50 °C.

are shown in Table 3. The PG increases with the reaction period. However, it should be noted that after 3.5 h, the increases in grafting level is marginal. The effect of time on grafting could be explained as follows : it is obvious that the longer the contact time of the monomer molecules with GG macro radical sites, the greater will be extent of grafting. The leveling of PG after a certain period (3.5 h) could be attributed to the depletion of initiator and monomer concentration with the progress of the reaction. The pH of the reaction mixture did not change throughout the reaction period, indicating the grafting process was not involved with the production of H⁺ or HO⁻.

Conclusion :

1,10-Phenanthroline plays an important role in the graft co-polymerization of vinyl monomers onto PVA using Fenton's reagent. The Fenton's reagent along with 0.1% phenanthroline may be considered as substitute for ceric ion in its activity. The optimum mole ratio of H₂O₂/Fe²⁺ is 55.5. The guar gum grafted with polymethyl methacrylate has better thermal stability than original starting polymer. The role of ferric ion is to produce GG macro-radicals. The pH of the reaction mixture did not change during graft polymerization.

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